

LEGAL AND SOCIAL ASPECTS OF PROVIDING INFORMATION SECURITY

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Abstract. This article talks about the problem of information security and its relevance in the modern world. Legal and social aspects of information security were also touched upon. The main purpose of information security and the scope of application of the concept of information security, as well as its application to society, are covered.

Key words: Cybersecurity, information, rights and freedoms, Internet, law, globalization, society.

INTRODUCTION

In the present era, when information and communication technologies are rapidly developing, it is known that the information resources of any country are one of the important factors determining its economic and military potential. Effective and rational use of this resource ensures the security of the country and the successful formation of a democratic information society. In such a society, the speed of information exchange increases, the use of advanced information and communication technologies for the collection, storage, processing and use of information is carried out on a large scale. At the same time, in the age of continuous application of various technologies, it has a significant impact on all areas of our daily life. Also, the speed of information exchange is becoming increasingly important in globalization, making information security and its protection an urgent issue. Today, the information society is formed with fast images, and the concept of state borders is disappearing in the world of information. The global computer network is gaining special importance in the socio-economic, political, spiritual and cultural life of the countries of the world. Therefore, information protection is an important state task in any country. The need for information protection in Uzbekistan is reflected in the creation of the state system of information protection and the development of the legal basis of information security.

In the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 12, 2002 "On Principles and Guarantees of Freedom of Information" [1], the state policy in the field of information security is aimed at regulating social relations in the information field and the individual, society and state's information it is determined that it is to ensure safety. "The adoption of the Law "On Principles and Guarantees of Freedom of Information" is important in the process of realizing the rights of every person to receive and use information freely and without hindrance, as well as in the protection of information, ensuring the information security of the individual, society and the state. gained importance»[2]

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on cyber security, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and information from Wikipedia were used in writing this article. Also, in the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on cyber security:[3] "The unified state policy in

the field of cyber security is determined by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the competent state body in the field of cyber security." important. Also, I. Karimov's "Basics of Information Security" and S. Ganiev's "Information Security" textbooks and training manuals were used.

NATIJARLAR

With ever-increasing reliance on technology and the Internet, citizens and organizations are constantly facing various cyber threats. Research shows that 60 percent of small businesses close after a cyber attack, highlighting the need for improved prevention strategies. Understanding why cyber security is important to today's society is essential in protecting ourselves and our personal information from potential harm.

At a briefing held with the representatives of the Department of Combating Crimes in the Field of Information Technologies of the Tashkent IIBB, the head of the Investigation Department of the IIBB Anvar Tokhtayev noted: "In 2022, 4,332 crimes were committed in Tashkent with the help of information technologies, or almost 2 times compared to 2021 (2,281) , compared to 2020 (106), 40 times more cybercrimes were committed. In most of the detected crimes (63.4 percent), money belonging to citizens was stolen through the Internet." [4]

As you can see, the largest 63.4% of crimes committed with the help of information technologies were cyber thefts. According to the data of February 2023, about 3 million people live in Tashkent, and about 4.5 million people come and go from other regions. Crimes committed in the field of information technology accounted for 96 per 100,000 population.

DISCUSSION

In order to combat these crimes, the Directorate for Combating Crime in the Information Technology Sector was opened within the IIBB. The management bank prepared videos aimed at preventing the robbery of money from plastic cards and covered them in the media. More than 2.5 million viewers watched it. As for the population that does not use the Internet, regional prevention inspectors interviewed more than 25,000 households. In addition, flyers were distributed to residents, and booklets were given to citizens in densely populated areas.

The task of ensuring information security is important. In order to ensure it, it is necessary to cooperate with legal, organizational measures and software and technical support (identification and authentication; access management; protocolization and audit; cryptography) (for example, at the level of enterprise management, its computer-internet information in order to ensure the security of the network, the development of the state policy related to the sector and the necessary resources are required). According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 188 of June 3, 2016 "On Electronic Government" [6] there is a "Principle of Information Security". According to it, state bodies providing public services must ensure information security of information systems and information resources used in the provision of electronic public services.

- Legal protection means protection of information by legal methods on the basis of legislation and normative legal documents that regulate the relations of subjects in the field of information protection, implement in practice and control their implementation. The methods of legal protection of information include the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan in this field, decrees and decisions of the President, decisions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers and other regulatory legal documents. In cases of violations of information access rules, information relationship participants, their rights and obligations, as well as legal regulations,

liability is considered at the legislative level and appropriate measures are taken. Organizational measures of protection are of an organizational nature and are measures designed to organize information system activities, employee relations, and user interactions with the system. Among these measures, the following important aspects can be pointed out:

- development of security policy;
- order entry and exit to the building;
- ordering permission to use the information system of employees;
- determining and providing responsibility in cases of non-compliance with information security requirements.

CONCLUSION

It is planned to develop the project "Strategy for ensuring cyber security in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2024-2026". This new strategy defines the main tasks of the further development of cyber security in digital economy sectors, measures and resources for the prevention of cybercrime, as well as the fight against it, ensuring the safe operation of information and important information infrastructure objects, as well as the innovative development of scientific and industrial institutions in the field of cyber security. directions and proposals are planned to be implemented.

It is worth mentioning that now, taking into account the proposals and recommendations of the relevant ministries and agencies, the "Roadmap" for the strategy of ensuring cyber security in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2024-2026 and its implementation is being formed.

Currently, the legal norms related to ensuring information security are only partially implemented compared to the priority tasks of the Republic of Uzbekistan established in the legislative documents, and they do not yet fully meet the current and current international trends in ensuring information and cyber security. At the same time, relations of mutual cooperation between state organizations and technical operators with the potential to monitor cyber attacks, prevent and sufficiently explain their damage, and take preventive measures have not yet been established.

References:

1. Ganiyev S.K. "Cyber Security Fundamentals". Study guide.
2. I. Karimov. "Basics of information security". Textbook.
3. Decision No. 188 of June 3, 2016 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Electronic Government".
4. Law of December 12, 2002 "On Principles and Guarantees of Freedom of Information".
5. <https://lex.uz> - national database of legislative information of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
6. <https://tace.uz> - the official website of the state unitary enterprise Cyber Security Center.
7. <https://www.gazeta.uz> – Uzbekistan news.